

DESIGN AND OPTIMIZATION OF A CRYOGENIC LIQUEFIED NATURAL GAS (LNG) STORAGE TANK FOR IMPROVED GAS RETENTION TIME

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ABSTRACT

Cryogenic LNG tanks is essential for the maintenance of low-temperature conditions needed for storing natural gas in its liquefied state, which significantly reduces volume and enables efficient transportation and storage. To retain the temperature of -162°C in a region where temperature fluctuates for a long-term storage system. This paper uses an advanced optimization and simulation tool to study structural integrity, thermal performance, and insulation properties of the storage tank. The authentic design configuration used 50,000 m³ LNG cryogenic storage tanks for the simulation. An initial temperature of -162°C and pressure of 3 bars and ambient temperature ranges of 18°C to 20°C and 25°C were used. The ANSYS simulation result showed an excellent design parameter with a heat leak and mass transfer rate range of 2.5% to 8% W/m²k with respect to time taken by the tank to absorb heat. The results demonstrate that an optimized tank design can significantly reduce boil-off gas (BOG) rates and operational costs while maintaining the structural stability and safety standards required for LNG storage. This paper presents valuable insights for the expansion of next-generation cryogenic storage systems, conducive to the sustainable and resourceful application of LNG in energy utilization.

Keywords: Design, Cryogenic, Storage Tank and Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG)

INTRODUCTION

Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG) has become an essential energy source owing to its cleaner burning properties, high energy concentration compared to traditional fossil fuels for transportation, and capacity to be stored and transported proficiently in a liquefied phase. As the demand for natural gas across the globe increases, there is an increasing need for forward-thinking storage solutions that guarantee economic viability, negligible energy loss, and ensure safety. The design and optimization of cryogenic storage tanks, which are accountable for maintaining LNG at very low temperatures (-162°C), are crucial to accomplishing these set objectives. Cryogenic LNG storage tanks are multifaceted schemes configured to contain high thermal gradients and pressures although curtailing boil-off gas (BOG) generation. BOG is known to be the vaporization of LNG as a result of heat ingress within the cryogenic system. Extreme BOG production poses a danger, increased cost of operating the tank system also leads to gas loss. Consequently, optimizing the design of LNG storage tanks is important to lengthen gas retention time, lessen energy loss, and improve the general productivity of LNG storage and delivery. Kim, J., & Lee, S. (2021).

This work offers an efficient method to the design and optimization of cryogenic LNG storage tanks, aimed at increasing gas retention time by abating heat transfer and mechanical failures. Through adopting an advanced simulation tool and method, the paper examines the influence of several design parameters, such as insulation material, tank geometry, and wall thickness, on thermal performance and structural integrity. The outcomes of this research provide a foundation for developing next-generation LNG storage systems that meet the stringent safety, efficiency, and sustainability standards required in the energy industry. Jeong-Soo, L. (2023).

With the push and improvement of clean energy commercialization around the globe and the rate of energy consumption in Nigeria due to population increase in recent years, there is need to develop a better system of natural gas storage. The consumption of natural gas in Nigeria and other Sub-Sahara African regions has seen an explosive expansion in current years owing to the removal of fuel subsidy (Aceves S. M., 2001). The production, processing and storage of natural gas or LNG plants in African countries will also cross the threshold of fast track. Furthermore, in order to meet the Nigerian government's gas master plan requirements, storage of the natural gas resources will be a major factor. Requirements for gas utilization in some states and local government areas will need the construction medium or large-sized LNG storage facilities. Some of the Key factors to be considered in the causes of the design of an LNG storage facility will include the pressure used for the operation and the temperature. For the operating pressure of an LNG cryogenic tank is calculated as - 1.0~29.0 kPa. G, while the calculated design temperature of the inner cryogenic tank is fixed at -162 °C. For the reason that the temperature within the internal tank system and the surrounding is not the same, this temperature difference leads to the production of heat. Because of this generation of heat input of the LNG tank, the design must take into consideration the material selection. The material selection for the design will be used to calculate the heat input to the tank and to insulation the wall which in turn limit the effect or flow of heat from the surrounding to the cryogenic system material. Lack of proper design insulation system will lead to large volume of boil-off gas production because the low-temperature gas will always tend to expand within the LNG tank due to heat flow and the result will be gasified LNG. Conditions that can lead to increase in boil-off gas is more heat flow or leakage, then production of boil-off gas (BOG) will be on the increase piercingly.

Considering the safety implication of much boil-off gas generation as a result of heat flow from the surrounding to the tank, certain design measures are taken. One measure will be the compressor selection and type because the type of compressor that will be selected will determine the energy consumption. Safety hazards will also be considered because treatment of the compressor due to energy consumption will lead to safety issues; hence the maximum acceptable boil-off gas rate of the cryogenic tank design is one the most vital gauge to determine the cryogenic insulation and cryogenic insulation effect of the LNG tank. Currently, the design and simulation requirements for the rate of evaporation of 150,000m³, 250,000m³ and still bigger LNG tanks are moderately mature, and the rate of boil-off gas ratio is needed to be within the range of 0.06%~0.08%/day under the working volume converted equivalent mass (wt), i.e. 0.06%~0.08wt%/day. For the tanks system of 350,000~180,000 m³ and small-sized cryogenic storage of 100,000m³, the rate of evaporation will be a function of the rate of heat flow and for now there is no standardized condition for the on a daily basis evaporation rate of an LNG small-sized tanks, normally this is determined by the plant operator and the construction engineer (Nwosi, et al, 2018).

The functions of Thermodynamic were utilized and put into operation numerically through a computer-aided simulation program. The resultant effect is based on the calculation of the liquefied natural gas cryogenic tank heat transfer, temperature, entropy change, mass transfer and computer simulation. This computer-based simulation is applied to obtain a number of comparatively high-quality analyses of the gas tank and the external containment of the tank performance. In order to determine the degree of boil-off gas that will be produced at a given time, the three-dimensional (3D) model design of the LNG cryogenic tank was configured via computer-aided design (CAD) software (Aceves S. M., 2001). Where a calculation of the heat transfer, the volume of the boil-off gas and the mass transfer determination was attained from a prototyped design using simulations like the computational fluid dynamics (CFD) approach; these involve the

application of the thermal conditions from ambient conditions and also forced thermal inclusion. The physio-chemical properties were further explored using a Computer Aided Engineering package (CAE) to simulate the real-life effect of the entire process. The Process flow diagram (PFD) of the process was deduced and calculated using the ASPEN HYSYS package which utilizes the thermodynamic models and process conditions to determining the outcome of the desired investigation. The CFD approach with the proper meshing of the model was carried out effectively. For the LNG tank simulation, the computational fluid dynamics consideration of the tank insulation material was analyzed.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Liquefied Natural Gas

Natural gas is produced from the wellbore with impurities and after conditioning which has to do with the removal of acid gases, water vapor, mechanical impurities, and other unwanted particles. The gas will be ready for extraction which is done to extract each of the components of the gas mixture through the use of specialized separators. For the production of liquefied natural gas, methane which is the major constituent of the natural will be required. Liquefied natural gas (LNG) is a ground-breaking technology that shows a high prospect for a better way of natural gas utilization, treatment, storage, management, and transportation (Bahadori, 2014). LNG is natural gas in liquid form with a reduced temperature of (-256°F) or in degree C, we record LNG to be having a temperature of (-162°C) and under an atmospheric pressure (1atm). At this point LNG is regarded or classified as a concentrated liquid gas that has been converted to liquid, for the reason that the process takes place at very low temperature below (-100°F) we also classify LNG as a cryogenic fluid. The primary purpose for liquefaction is to gather more volume for easy transport of the gas to far distances. Today, energy is the building block of all civilized world and the most central areas in the world energy outlook in recent years has been energy sources. In all, both renewable and non-renewable, natural gas presents a clean energy sources to mitigate climate change due to green-house, hazardous gases emissions (environmental pollution), and the cost of production. Another huge advantage associated with the process of NG Liquefaction, is that after the gas is decreased in volume to liquid fluid by the time its converted back to gaseous outward or physical appearance its volume expands and increase to the degree of six hundred (600) times (Adom, et al, 2010).

Storage of Natural Gas

Due to seasonal fluctuations in the demand for gas for space heating, the total gas demand generally varies considerably from summer to winter. One way to accommodate this demand would be to build a pipeline from the gas fields large enough to supply the greatest amount of gas that would be needed in the winter; to make better use of the pipeline throughout the year, the gas distributors have acquired more heating customers than the pipelines have been able to supply in the middle of winter. Today the main storage possibilities of natural gas are as follows; (Ikoku, CU. 1984): Natural gas storage in pipelines, underground natural gas storage in depleted fields, underground natural gas storage in aquifers, natural gas storage under high pressure in steel reservoirs. Natural gas storage by natural gas solution in propane, Liquefied natural gas (LNG) storage, and underground natural gas storage in man-made caverns. The gas stored in the above ways is available for withdrawal during times of peak demand to supply the fuel market. This susceptibility to being stored and later withdrawn is one of the characteristics of natural gas that adds to its flexibility and usefulness.

The energy which causes the gas to move from the storage reservoir to the well head and the market is the energy that is built in by compressors at the time the gas is stored by Wartsilä Corporation. (2015). This in-built energy is, of course, made possible by the compressibility and expandability of the gas. National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) 2017 technical report. The fact that gas exists under pressure in oil reservoirs is a fact of considerable economic significance in the production of crude oil. Where the gas not only moves the oil to the wellbore as it expands but also supplies the pressure to lift the oil to the surface, the oil is recovered in greater volume and at less cost than would be true if they were absent. In this sense, then, gas under pressure in an underground reservoir possesses energy of two kinds: first, there is the energy that may be released in the form of heat by combustion; and second, there is the physical energy in the form of pressure supplied by nature which makes recovery of other hydrocarbons simpler and less expensive. University of Texas (1956)

LNG Storage Tank Evaporation System

To reduce or minimize the heat flow or input within the storage system is the key function of the insulation of a cryogenic LNG tank. The other main aspect is to control the volume of rate of evaporation of the tank. Some other consideration is ensuring that the gas is stored for a long time. The natural gas key component is methane (CH₄), and it has been calculated that the thermodynamic three-phase application is below 0°C. Due to this thermodynamic point the gas cannot be "liquefied" using pressurization similar to LPG at normal room condition. Therefore, when the temperature is reduced to -162 °C through liquefaction process LNG can be produced. Consequently, LNG is not the same as the regular fuels such as LPG, diesel, gasoline and other hydrocarbons, and pressurization is used to reduce its volatilization. At the same time, the function of the cryogenic insulation structure needs to protect the non-low temperature components of the storage tank (mainly the outside of the storage tank) to keep it at the required ambient temperature, limit the damage of the foundation or soil at the bottom of the storage tank due to frost heaving, and prevent and minimize the condensation and icing of water vapor on the external surface of the storage tank (Chen, et al, 2014).

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Materials

The research design for this work was based on simulations involving thermodynamic properties, insulation materials, cryogenic tank, natural gas, liquefied natural gas. Thermodynamic consideration of Models, continuing functions, equations, variables involving pressure, temperature, heat and mass transfer and flow rates was utilized from real data sourced from literature. The three-dimensional (3D) model of the cryogenic tank was achieved using a computer aided design (CAD) package where the boil-off gas determination was attained from a prototyped design using numerical simulations like the computational fluid dynamics (CFD) approach. This involves using thermal conditions from ambient conditions and also forced thermal inclusion. The physio-chemical properties were further explored using a Computer Aided Engineering package (CAE) to simulate in real-life effect of the entire process. The Process flow diagram (PFD) of the process was deduced and calculated using the ASPEN Hysys package which utilizes the thermodynamic models and process conditions to determining the outcome of the desired investigation. The CFD approach with proper meshing of the model was carried out effectively.

Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG) Feed Characterization

Liquefied Natural Gas characterization was collected from different gas companies and each of the collected samples were analysed with respect to each products composition, Methane component mole fraction percentages, the advanced calorific value ((20⁰C (-3.98bar), (25⁰C, (°C, 1.01bar)) and ((30⁰C, 6.01bar) in that order, Average molecular weight (kg/k.mol), density (kg/m³(n)), Specific Gravity (relative density), minor calorific value, higher specific energy KJ/Kg, boiling point at atmospheric pressure and the Wobbe Index which in this case is look upon as the measure of the value of heat contribution to LNG in any application, the Wobbe index is a derivative of a standard of measure from the equation of orifice flow.

Table 1: Liquefied Natural Gas Characterization

Components		Mole %
Methane	CH4	92.215%
Ethane	C2H6	4.841%
Propane	n-C3H8	2.111%
Butane	n-C3H10	0.360%
Iso-butane	i-C3H10	0.381%
Pentane	n-C5H12	0.018%
Iso-Pentane	i-C5H12	0.003%
Nitrogen	N ₂	0.000%
Molecular Weight (kg/k mol)		17.646
Density (Kg/m ³ (n))		0.7897
Specific Gravity (Relative Density)		0.6107
Units of Measure	MJ/m ³ (n)	kWh/m ³ (n)
Advanced Calorific Value	4.321	12.00
Minor Calorific Value	39.05	10.85
Wobbe Index (on Hs)	55.30	15.36

Method

The method includes a Cryogenic Tank Multi-Layer Shielding and Insulation (MLI) design and a computer-based simulation. The multi-layer shielding and tank insulation are a technology developed by cryogenic engineers to handle the technical difficulty of unregulated temperature and pressure Marques, et, al (2023).. This challenge could lead to pressure build-up, increase in temperature, and explosion as a result of improper design calculation and material selection. MLS and MLI were used to make adequate cryogenic tank design considerations within the internal region. There are several types of excessive heat flux and transfer control and preventive measures or technology. The equation for the calculation of the Multi-Layer Shielding system is presented in equation (1.) and for n shields in association with the system emissivity ϵ , the heat transfer exchange consideration is based on.

$$q_r = \left(\frac{\epsilon}{(n+1)(2-\epsilon)} \right) \sigma (T_1^4 - T_2^4) \quad (1.)$$

Which is defined in such a way that considering the factor of $1/n + 1$, the emissivity $\epsilon \ll 1$, and it is reduced to q_r . Hence the analysis is based on the fact that the distribution of temperature shield across the tank system in not uniformly circulated, for the reason that the heat transfer exchange is not linear.

Description of the Entire Process

The structural diagram of the LNG storage tank system followed a series of feed gas sample analysis and the definition of the composition. All critical parameters have been analyzed. From the cryogenic storage tank, the LNG stream is defined as the inlet while the external heat stream is sourced from the atmospheric or ambient temperature. The atmospheric heat impact of 25⁰C as against -162⁰C LNG temperature stored tank internal temperature produced sufficient feed gas that is controlled through the flow line to the compressor where it is compressed to a non-return valve to the control volume as presented in Fig. 1 above. From this point the feed gas is pressurized with an increase in temperature to meet the engine specification for fuel combustion.

Fig. 1: Vertical Structural view of LNG storage tank development.

The cryogenic tank system consists of nozzle, cryogenic ball valve, LNG supply feed line, Vent, Safety relief valve, LNG flow meter, Gauge and LNG supply feed line to engine. The fluid in the cryogenic tank (LNG) is separated into four parts: the vapour phase space, the thermal or heat leak region, the core body area, the system boundary layer. The storage tank is designed to contain 30,000 liters volume of LNG in a cryogenic tank. The setup contains 30,000kg LNG sample, the 30,000kg was used as the capacity of LNG in the cryogenic tank with the volume, which is 18,000,000 scf LNG equivalent when regasified as used in the stored tank. The cryogenic tank includes an intake nozzle which is the LNG supply feed line, it serves as the intake gas supply unit, the Vent unit is used to ventilate the thermal overfill which is not allowed to build up, an unstable storage condition will result a major safety issue (Musa, Md. Zakaria, et al 2012).

Tank Design Model Assumptions

We assume that the volume and mass of the LNG tank is 30,000 M³ and 30000kg respectively. The LNG cryogenic stored tank product is assumed as sink; the heat source is the ambient condition or the atmospheric surrounding. Thermal conductivity, k (Watts/m/⁰C) is not state dependent or temperature. For the Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG) cryogenic tank system design, certain considerations are very critical prior to designing the tank. As a matter of fact, we look at

the material selection that will be able to withstand extremely low temperature tank configuration. The tank Sizing, Rating, Volume m^3 of the tank, tank diameter (m), Length, head height (m), Nozzles, Heat loss, level of taps, tank geometry and orientation, flat cylindrical and horizontal and the shape of the tank (Jiang & Li, 2013).

Table 2: Stored Tank Design Dimensions

S/N	Rating	Head Height (m)	Volume (M^3)	29452.431 M^3
1	Geometry	Flat Cylinder	Diameter (m)	25 (m)
2	Orientation	Horizontal	Length (m)	60 (m)

The length and diameter of the tank which are in meters are calculated to be 25 meters and 60 meters correspondingly while the total volume capacity of the tank is calculated to be 30,000 M^3 the detailed design dimensions are presented in the figure 2: as show below.

Simulated Cryogenic Tank Cycle Main Parameters

Table 3: Required Insulating Material Thickness for Spherical Storage Vessels for LNG

	C_p ($J\ Kg^{-1}\ K^{-1}$)	μ ($Pa\ s$)	K ($Wm^{-1}K^{-1}$)	ρ ($kg\ m^3$)	Emissivity
Perlite	UDF	-	387	50	0.55
Air	1006.43	$1.79e^{-5}$	0.0242	1.225	
LNG	3450	$1.46e^{-4}$	0.193	424.53	
Methane	2222	$1.09e^{-5}$	0.0332	0.6679	

Table 4: Thermal Conductivity of Glass Wool Insulations for Boundary Temperatures of $-162^\circ c$ and $(-139^\circ F)$ and of Foam Insulations for Boundary Temperatures of 300k ($80^\circ F$) & 77k ($-139^\circ F$)

Foam	Thermal Conductivity			
	Kg/m^3	Ib_m/m^3	$mW/m-K$	$Btu/hr-ft-F$
Polyurethane	11	0.70	33	0.019
Polystyrene	39	2.4	33	0.019
Rubber	80	5.0	36	0.021
Silica	160	10.0	55	0.032
Glass Wool;	140	8.7	35	0.020

Table 5: The Characteristics of the BOG to be liquefied are the Following

Density (100 % Methane):	$425\ kg/m^3$
Minimum temperature:	$-163^\circ C$
Tank volume:	$294300\ m^3$ and 95 % tank filling
Design volume of BOG	0.15 % of cryogenic tank volume per day

Table 6: BOG-composition (mole %)

Methane	84-100 %
BOG pressure:	1.03 bars

Table 7: Compressor Operating Parameters

Suction Pressure:	1.03 bars
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Suction Temperature:	-120°C
Discharge Pressure:	2.5 bar
Discharge Temperature:	-31°C (100 % CH ₄)

Initially, an experiment was conducted for proper material selection to determine the appropriate cryogenic tank that will hold LNG in a sport utility vehicle for a calculated period (48 hours) and a liquefied natural gas sample of 30,000kg was used to test run, and 1m² surface area of the cryogenic tank. For an LNG tank carrier with an expected boil-off gas generation for immediate use, one of the major factors to be considered is the impact of the atmospheric heat or the thermal Radiation from room temperature which is above the LNG temperature and is the main source of boil-off gas production and also is one of the main heat loads in cryogenic systems. Afonso et, al (2023).

Table 8: Consumption of cryogenic insulation materials for LNG storage tank when BOR is 0.06, 0.08, 0.09, 0.11, [wt%/day] respectively

Daily Evaporation rate	Elastic felt [m ²]	Expanded perlite [m ³]
0.06%	1200	3206
0.08%	1200	2150
0.09%	1200	1100
0.011%	1200	1000

The Emissivity in the case is the LNG tank carrier property of the exterior material that establishes and decides the division of radiant flux that is engrossed or emitted. Emissivity ϵ depends on material conductivity, temperature. ϵ Is also a function of wavelength, but engineering usually relies on average values measured for range of temperatures.

Fig. 2: Cryogenic Tank Design with Dimensions

The Nickel Steel material was selected. A look at the basis for refrigeration as to maintaining the initial temperature of the system when the vehicle is static and when it is in motion because excessive boil-off gas can lead to explosion due to pressure surge and build-up within the tank. Another significant factor to be considered is the Heat exchange medium within the tank and the Thermal insulation of the system for the prevention and control of heat leakages. The American Society of Testing and Materials (ASTM) set out the specifications for the material requirement

for the design of very low-temperature substances Effendy, et, al (2017). The ASTM A353 code is the specification for nine percent (9%) nickel steel plates for cryogenic tanks that are double-normalized, and nickel steel is also applied for low-temperature substances container welded pressure vessels. Ordinary steel usually has two or more slip systems within a very freeze-up temperature. The area considered as two (2.) is the tank inlet valve with control elements attached, such as volume gauge and three (3.) is the outlet valve also with control element attached, such as pressure build-up relief systems.

$$\frac{d(\text{heat flux})}{dx} + \text{Heat sink } k \text{ per unit volume} = 0$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(-k \frac{du}{dx} \right) + q(u.x) = 0 \quad (2.)$$

Where

u = the temperature of Nodal in °C;

k = Thermal conductivities measured in Watts/m/°C;

q = The Heat sink for each unit volume in Joules/m³;

x = Distance of outer wall of outer spherical to inner wall of inner spherical shell in meters

The central equation can be a consideration of forcing the residual to be zero in a spatially averaged good judgment. Resolving equations using the finite element approximation we divide the domain of the LNG tank into three major separated lengths to form the node. Each of the different lengths represents the node of the finite elements of continues unit field variable inside every one element by the approximation of parametric finite element. The temperature of the system is uniformly distributed or is homogeneous for the vapor-liquid phase which is represented as (T_g) and (T_l) for each phase is considered as one with inter-phase heat transfer. The consequence of the turbulence of the host vehicle motion is not account for. A look at the energy balance for the liquid phase may be described as below:

$$\frac{d}{dt} (mh)_l = Q_l - \dot{m}_b h_{g,i} \quad (3.)$$

Where the boil-off rate is represented by the m_b and the enthalpy of the gas liquid is written as $h_{g,i}$, now the corresponding rate of heat transfer to the liquid phase is received from atmospheric air and the radiator heat flow line from this process.

The Conceptual Framework of the Simulation Process

For the process design, the cryogenic tank design was first initiated to attain the appropriate three-dimensional (3D) model design parameters with the aid of a computer aided engineering design (CAED) tool. The Autodesk inventor professionals was used for the tank actual sizing in view of the fixed LNG volume capacity of (30,000Kg) LNG that was used, three-dimensional 3D, the data for the tank sizing was inputted into the software. The model for net energy conservation: The fluid stored tank (LNG) is partitioned in layers of four: The boundary, thermal region, the core and the vapour phase, analysis through the ANSYS application. ANSYS, ANSYS CFD Reference Manual, 12.0 ed., ANSYS Inc., 2009 Arcelor Mittal (2017) USA

Simulation Environment Based Modeling

The SRK- equation of state (EOS) and the PR were the basis for fluid packages definition for the simulation model as follows:

$$P = \frac{RT}{v - b} - \frac{a(T)}{v(v + b)} \quad (4.)$$

$$a(T) = 0.42747 \frac{R^2 T_c^2}{P_c} \alpha(T) \quad b = 0.0867 \frac{RT_c}{P_c} \quad (5.)$$

For all pure substances, this equation was modified by Soave in a straightforward outline for $\alpha \equiv \alpha(T_r, \omega)$ looking at the improvement of the theory of the acentric factor of Pitzer (Wang B. 2010). There were several evaluations by Soave on the best model for predicting vapor pressure from his improvements of the initial SRK EOS. After testing some substances, it was discovered that his adjustment significantly enhanced vapor pressure predictions. Where $\alpha(T)$ is extrapolated for the supercritical temperatures. cryospain.com

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The feed gas composition of methane of percentage in deferent scenarios is long-established to be 84.5%, 89.63%, 90.28%, 92.21%, 95.44%, from deferent LNG sources as shown in table 1 for the simulation proper the standard of methane composition is set at 100%. In line with the IMO recommended standard for IGC conditions on cryogenic tank design consideration parameters configuration for ambient temperature ought to be 20°C to 25°C, 30°C to 35°C and 40 °C to 45°C in that order depending on region. Hence for the ambient temperature consideration for this simulation is set at 20°C to 25°C as starting points.

Table 9: Methane Critical Properties (Huang Q., Xia F. 2010)

	Atmospheric Boiling Point (°C)	Liquid SG [15°C/15°C]	Gas SG [Air = 1]	Flammability Limits [Vol. % in Air]
Methane	-161.5	(0.30)	apparent	0.554 5.0/15.0

Table 10: Cryogenic tank dynamics (Jeong-Soo LEE. Young-Soo RYU. 2009)

Dynamics	Model Details	Vessel Volume [m ³]	2.89
Specs	Initialize From Products	Vessel Diameter [m ³]	0.25
Holdup	Dry Start up	Length [m]	0.59
Strip Chart	Initialize From User	Liq. Volume Percent [%]	75.0
Heat Exchanger	Lag Rxn Temperature	Liq. Percent Level [%]	75.0
Dynamic	Feed Delta P [KPa] (0.00)	Level Calculator	Hori Cylinder
Specifications	Vessel Pressure [KPa] (101.3)	Fraction Calculator	Levels & Nozzles

Solutions to Cryogenic Tank Design and Dimensions

The design of the stored tank was embarked on through simulation, the design of the tank using Autodesk Inventor Exported into ANSYS (Multi-physics) using the space claim. Reactor discretized into nodes and elements in order to determine the wall thickness and heat fluctuation, flux and distribution flow into the system. The tank is designed in a method that the required boil-off gas will be produced as expected with respect to the insulation of the tank wall thickness and the appropriate dimension and materials as shown in figure 4.1 the materials for the stored tank insulation for the heat flux effect was Glass Wool, this is due to the material quality and the

capacity to regulate the flow of heat from the environment through the wall of the tank to the annulus and to the first layer of the system. The tank B (1.3) is the inlet valve for the feed gas stream while the area labeled A (1:3) is the outlet valve for the passage of the produced boil-off gas to the valve connecting the compressor flow line. At the interior part of the stored it is designed such that the volume of the LNG, the rate at which the feed gas is supply and extent at which the storage will last are momentous determinants of the prospective boil-off gas characteristics and performance.

With the appropriate heat flux of $1.5 \text{ W/m}^2\cdot\text{K}$ and the temperature of 298K the required boil-off will be produced and the actual result of the volume produced per second based on the volume of storage will be archived through simulation. The accurate material for insulation and coating and the design dimensions has been established. The tank inlet and outlet nozzles has been estimated and measured to the internal and external radius of 25.4 and 16.7. ANSYS R18.1 as utilized presents the accurate shape and size of the stored tank after the inventor analysis and the selection of internal and external insulation materials with appropriate annulus dimensions. With respect to the thickness of the stored tank insulation materials and the annulus, the increase in the thickness of insulation with glass wood material offers the needed heat flux as shown in figure 3 of 0.1 within -162°C LNG temperature. The thickness has great impact on the heat flux into the system, the chart showed the thickness (M) insulation against flux (Joule and M2) of heat into the tank where the LNG is stored. The conditions of the system boundary bring about the detailed definition of the operating provision of the configuration and the entire system process. The material used for the tank design is one factor we used to determine some aspect of the condition. The temperature of the vaporized gas leaving the tank and the tank pressure build-up owing to the gas molecule expansion are another factor.

Fig. 3: Solution to ANSYS Discretised, Meshing into Nodes and Elements

The evaporation and the combustion at the point of the engine, the engine tail gas releasing and outlet temperature, build-up of the pressure and flow rates are the prominent parameters that were recorded and make use of in the simulation and derived models from literature. An additional condition of operation entails the ambient temperature of the area or location of the vehicle containing LNG for combustion. The weight of the tank, the density of the LNG, and the ambient condition jointly are required to determine the nearness of the fluid boil-off formation. The interesting aspect of the simulation was the consideration of the kind of heat transfer that is taking place between the surrounding and the stored tank which is the convective heat transfer coefficient. This heat transfer process was applied to act on the stored tank LNG as it was assumed that the

vehicle conveying the product may be on static motion or may also be on motion to determine each level of gas vaporization. The overall interest of these is conducted to establish the spread of the heat flux for the duration of the mixing and integration of the liquid and gaseous phases of the LNG. chartindustries.com. At this point, the spread of heat flux or propagation is measured via the computer-aided engineering application in use. This is regulated in teams of the intensity of heat progression towards the stored tank lower temperature region and the higher temperature fluid region which in this situation is the inner tank outer layer as against the core or center region of the stored tank. The basic principle behind the determination of HTC in cryogenic tank is system wall-function-based model which is applied here through the treatment of kinetic energy turbulence, temperature, density, pressure and specific heat as shown in equation 1.

$$h_{eff} = \frac{p C_p C_\mu^{1/4} K_P^{1/2}}{T^*} \quad (6.)$$

In this case the C_p represents the specific heat capacity while the K_P indicates the turbulence Kinetic energy at point P, and T^* is the pressure and temperature as defined in ANSYS FLUENT 6.3 as the basis for the computer application simulation of the FLUENT. Although this is basically for unconventional cases cum adiabatic system walls and also accessible simply when the fluid flow is turbulent and the energy equation is made possible or enabled.

Computational Fluid Dynamics Heat transfer

The solution to the CFD was achieved through the input data of the software heat transfer models. All the necessary assumption made in chapter three was the basis of obtaining the CFD result. The convective boundary heat transfer of $1.5 \text{ W/m}^2 \text{ K}$ and a free stream temperature of 298k for the stored tank wall zone material. With a flow direction moving from the z direction to x direction and an air fluid zone area and board solid zone casing. The cryogenic tank containing LNG with 162°C temperature and in an environment of ambient temperature of 77°F with pressure of 1 bar and tank internal pressure of 2 bars owing to the LNG molecular expansion undergoing through heat flux input, the temperature distribution of a convective heat transfer cum mesh, vector and the mach contours is as shown in figure 4. The estimation and evaluation of BOG rate is fundamental for developing an LNG process with key interest in heat leakage. Several literature researches scrutinized BOG rate basically in LNG workstations, maritime units and immobile containers. The assumptions or hypothesis has been only for surface evaporation of liquid cum BOG rate estimated as % of its initial volume.

$$BOR = \frac{Q * 360 * 24}{\Delta H * V_{LNG} * \rho} * \quad (7.)$$

100

BOR indicates daily basis % of BOG (%/d), V_{LNG} , volume of LNG in tanks in m^3 , ρ = LNG density in kg/m^3 , Q = heat exchange in W and ΔH = latent heat of evaporation in J/kg . Still, BOR equation does not explain vapor increase within tank internal and detailed analysis of heat transfer to tank (Li H. R., Xu J. (2012). Modeled mass transfer rate of LNG from liquid to gaseous phase, tied their model using ANSYS FLUENT they proved temperature and BOG characterization and foretell an entire rate of evaporation inside a motion and motionless LNG tanks, similar approach was used to archive our heat transfer result as show in Figure 4.

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Mass – Transfer – Rate} \\ & = \frac{r * VF_l * \rho_l (T_l - T_{sat})}{T_{sat}} \end{aligned} \quad (8.)$$

r = under relaxation factor, VF_l = liquid volume fraction, ρ_l = liquid density, T_l = liquid temperature and T_{sat} = saturated temperature. This work uses equation 3.51 to model the absolute rate transfer of heat, mass and evaporation of 30000kg LNG cryogenic tank via UDF in ANSYS FLUENT. Li, Z., Wang, et, al (2024). Looking at the occurrence of natural convection, we realized that the moment it takes place in a system such as this case the fluid in question gains heat and at this point the density of the fluid expands with variation in its temperature. Hence the fluid flow is acted upon or stimulated by of gravitational force performing on fluid density disparity and variation.

Result of Simulated Parameters

All the relevant parameters were well defined at the preliminary stage of the simulation. The basic parameters such as the once that has to do with the influx of heat, the condition, properties, composition and the process flow specification were considered as stated in table 5. At this point the LNG vapour is produced at the surface or top of the fluid and it is feed to the compressor suction unit as the flow continues with 1% increase as shown in the boil-off column. There is a little change in the temperature of the gas, because of this change in temperature the initial pressure also increases with respect to time.

The graphical plot of the heat interaction with the tank and the flow of the vapor respectively points towards the confirmation that LNG is one of most transport fuel with high volume retention as illustrated in the two-graph plot. In this case there is no re-liquefaction method as our major interest has been for the LNG to vaporize at a given time with control systems. The external heat flow was set at 2.250 [kJ/h] that influenced the BOG also increased the pressure to be slightly high to 4.5 bars, towards the end of the process flow and against 1 bar starting point. BOG flows from the top of the internal configuration of the thermo-cool system with an optimal temperature and with a extremely low vapour fraction. The process is designed for an automatic capacity control from 40% to 100% cum an utmost efficiency at 80 % of the ostensible vaporized capacity. In line with the IMO IGC specification for the design simulated parameters when considering an atmospheric temperature of 20°C - 25 °C and 32°C and LNG temperature of 162°C.

Fig. 6: Graph of pressure build-up of internal zone of tank due to increase in temperature, from 20°C to 40°C.

The pressure increased from 101kpa to the point of 140kpa which means that pressure based on temperature profile of the tank can be ascertained and controlled in under to prevent excessive pressure surge in the tank, as the temperature increased the pressure also increased, drop in the temperature as a result of heat flux is one of the factors used to determine the pressure build-up in the tank because based on this scenario can develop an appropriate pressure gauges and safety materials to regulate the system pressure configuration. Other factors worth of mentioning are the thickness of the wall tank, the material selection for the manufacturing of the tank, the sizing, volume and the density of the stored fluid in the tank. Fluid mechanics of the vapor process, LNG cryogenic tankers hold in a fluid that the density is reduced amount more than that air and seawater at point when the fluid evaporates and boil-off gas is formed. All the produced vapor as part of the initial assumption will always be formed at the surface of the LNG with which retain its initial temperature of -162°C and the moment the temperature is reduced to -152°C which -10°C then we begin to observe patch up of the gas from the liquid phase and this is determine by a velocity which the attained based on the difference in pressure involving the atmospheric and the LNG tank pressure.

Fig. 7: Increase in Temperature versus Time for Heat Generation

A numerical simulation conducted using Finite Element Analysis (FEA) and ANSYS CFD.

The preliminary numerical simulation conducted applying the Finite Element Analysis (FEA), design volume and the tank sizing of 20 liters while the tank heat flux as simulated for 5hr/day was $0.00157\text{Kw}/\text{m}^2$ and the walls at $0.00448\text{Kw}/\text{m}^2$ is presented in Figure 7 also the impact of the ambient heat flow (KJ/h) and the system mass flow rate of the LNG BOG generation (kg) plot is shown in Figure 8. The software calculated the heat leakage into the system with temperature increase assumed per hour in a day was set at 1.3 W and pressure set at 1 bar at the initial stage. The LNG mass flow rates from the ANSYS primary Simulation result was recorded as 1.2%, - 1.4% and 1.6% to 15% of the total LNG stored tank volume with respect to increase in the value of heat flux into the system at different simulation and time taken by the tank to absorb the heat. The results as estimated using ANSYS indicated that LNG cryogenic tank BOG generation as

presented in Figure 8 the Ambient Heat (KJ/h) and Mass Flow Rate of LNG Boil-off gas production (kg) based on the plot the results are 0.0187%, 0.0551% and 0.09262% correspondingly. While the result of the outlet velocity was recorded at 0.867m/s and the LNG temperature initialized at -155°C, while the tank pressure equals 1.2bar.

Fig. 8: Ambient Heat (KJ/h) Vs. Mass Flow Rate of LNG BOG Production (kg) plot

Through the CAE software the verification was made possible based on the input simulation data, FEA by means of the CFD Mesh and the fluent computation model established and presented in this thesis, 25 liters LNG storage cryogenic tank and the volume that was contain (0.4) was observed to be adequate appropriate. Subsequent to series of test running with various tank sizing, volume, temperature, pressure and the material selection it was discovered that as the heat flow continues to increase from 1 ((KJ/h)) to 4 ((KJ/h)), the mass flow rates of LNG Boil-off gas production at different percentage increase in the heat flux resulted into 0.012kg/s to 0.043kg/s as presented in figure 8 which the ambient heat (KJ/h) in opposition to the mass flow rate of the LNG Boil-off gas production (kg) plot.

CONCLUSION

The findings demonstrate that properly designed LNG cryogenic tanks can significantly reduce boil-off gas (BOG) losses, improve energy efficiency, and extend the storage life of LNG. By optimizing insulation and pressure control, the study suggests ways to enhance both the operational reliability and economic viability of LNG storage systems. The paper concludes with recommendations for tank design improvements and future developments in LNG cryogenic storage technology. The design and simulation of Liquefied natural gas (LNG) cryogenic tank was conducted through engineering-based software's. Owing to the increase in the population of Nigeria and domestic use of LNG. The need to develop storage system for distribution of LNG is very significant. One of the important processing and storage equipment of the LNG distribution, receiving, storage terminal is a cryogenic tank. This design can be manufactured in real life for industrial processes. The paper recommends that LNG cryogenic storage can be designed, via assessment of existing storage columns, gathering of optimum daily evaporation rate supplies of

the insulation system. We recommend strong legislation to put an end to natural gas flaring in line with mandate to sustain the environment from dangerous gas pollution. LNG storage for stationary and mobile system is highly recommended.

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